

Sports Training Activities Of Para-Academic Rowers And Its Safety Rules

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Abstract: *The main tasks of the coach are to challenge the athletes every day, to encourage them to physical education and sports, to unite them and to place in their hearts the spiritual foundations of physical education and sports.*

Keywords — rowing, continuous sequence of movements, dynamic balance, water sports basics, safety vest.

INTRODUCTION

Human desired movement activity his external to the environment mutually active effect as a result done increases . External environment - external environment and natural external to the environment separate acceptance done Para oar to hear in sports artificial (controlled) external the environment is this boat , oar , oar to hear of the basin conditions , natural external environment and the earth atmosphere of the earth weight power , from this except to himself special features have has been water environment . Para oar of the listener to himself specific movement activity this his two in the environment is movement : air environment and water environment Sportsman all mechanic things the air in the environment done increases . And this physiological processes - energy supply , thermoregulation processes pass complicates . Oar through the boat to move while water in the environment done increases . This is a paddle to hear of sports to himself unique , unrepeatable feature is considered

On the boat sitting outside environment with mutually effect as a result oar rider the boat movement provider actions complex performs These actions high coordination complexity with is characterized . Oar to hear different sports in types to the eye throw away differences regardless oar of the listener basic movement activity organize doer one how much common to the laws to be can

Cyclicity is a para oar rider training and competition in the activity many cycle actions performs Through this don't move high automated to the level of sports equipment high to the capacity of the cycle all element and structural parts in sync to be fulfilled is achieved .

Actions continuously sequence — paraacademic oar to hear of sports all types of the technique important is a feature . Hand and oar movement elliptical in trajectory , body parts and the direction of the oar movement without stopping execution it is necessary Through this your actions mutually compliance and to fit is achieved .

Muscle consecutively reduction and relaxation cyclicity at work high the work ability save important condition is considered That's right , an oar to hear sports with in dealing with all muscle groups complete not loose , for example , the

situation storage and oar to catch provider muscle groups stress is supported .

Unstable on the support dynamic balance storage oar to hear movement activity in sports to himself special structural part is considered On the boat balance storage situation regularly control to do and manage at the expense of done is increased . Technician improvement as a result balance storage skill automatic , athlete perception of technique important structural parts (tempo, rhythm , rhythm amplitude , voltage) control to do , from this besides , tactical tasks to solve is directed .

Oar of the listener main activity people for relatively unusual in water conditions done increases . of the boat coup not only new to engage started in athletes perhaps everyone practitioners is also negative for consequences take coming can of the organism hard cold , seizure , lat to eat and shock these are including These are between even to death take there are visitors . That's why for oar to hear sports training and competitions in detail thinking developed safety system with to be provided necessary

Water sports bases rescue service organize to do base leadership undertake is loaded . They are in the water security provide of order sure regulation to compose they have to Water sports bases leadership is individual and group rescue of means existence watching to go a must Training in the process rescue service task directly coach in charge of will be That's why for coach oar to hear sports for special was risks account to get and regularly prevention their work take to go forced

To the circle sorting during coach new of the practitioner swim to get check it is necessary To swim those who do not know to training to swim until he learns until to the boats will not be transferred . Oar to hear sports with to engage those who want first to swim they know and boats when it is born how by doing the first help to show from learning after to the boats to get off permission is given From this each except engaged in in training safety his vest from wearing after to water to get off permission will be done .

Technique safety rules with engaged in introduction

T/r	CONTENT
1	Active age, with sports minimum age of participants requirements suitable coming a must
2	Employee himself in the account standing from the polyclinic which group disability (group I-II-III) . about reference present to do a must
3	Employee swim get qualification occupied to be a must
4	Employee to water exit for from the coach permission take a must
5	Employee to water from exit before safety his vest to wear a must
6	In the water movement during engaged in on the coast ra n a to places to go is prohibited .
7	new engaged in in the water coach to see within the limit movement a must
8	To the water a boat beak to the flow against towards to put a must
9	Employees oar to hear equipment the eye like a pupil protection to do a must
10	Busy safety rules with acquaintance about introduction to the paper hand put and confirm a must

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Initial training from 1.5-2 meters deep didn't happen in basins spent ok Each training before coach personally , equipment , boat and oar , individual and group protection of means validity check a must

Summary : Training wrong organize doing , training styles wrong selection , competition took preparation is different stages sportsman organism functional of possibilities very strain take will come . For this reason coach surface came your diseases the first appearances notice take and to them own on time measures to see , from this except for athletes own on time doctor apparently that they pass control by doing standing it is necessary

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